

SYNTHESIS AND APPLICATION OF ALIGNED, DISCONTINUOUS COMPOSITES

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A family of materials is being developed to fill the large processing gap which exists between ideal unidirectional sheet and those random mats and fabrics which are easier to form into components, but which then display lower properties, because control of fibre orientation has been sacrificed. Aligned prepreg mats of short carbon fibres had shown some promise for the purpose; they could be stretched both axially and transversely, plied to produce the rotational extension observed in fabrics, and gave adequate mechanical properties in moulded test panels.

Recent work on a centrifugal process of fibre deposition has led to more precise alignment of discontinuous fibres and consequent increases of fibre packing in the prepreg mat. It was then found, using HTS carbon, that the tensile strength of these unidirectional mouldings was less than ten percent below that of equivalent continuous fibre mouldings. This has led to a wider evaluation of discontinuous composites in many aerospace applications, and the process itself now produced aligned prepreg sheet about two metres by one metre in size.

This paper is mainly concerned with two further developments. The first is the detailed measurement of limiting flow properties of the basic prepreg and the way these vary with orientation and with plying arrangements. The resultant strength and variability of mouldings has also been measured, together with the effect of the loading regime used to produce the flow.

New forming procedures for components have been evolved, e.g. to retain control of fibre alignment while shaping complex and re-entrant shells. The advantage is emphasized of planned rotation of alignment directions during shaping, but in the particular case of cross-ply prepreg, a direct comparison can also be made with the draping behaviour of fabrics.

The second development is concerned with hybrid fibre composites. The centrifugal process provides ideal conditions in which to form intimately-mixed hybrids e.g. carbon fibre-glass fibre and carbon fibre-carbon fibre. It has thus been confirmed that an increase does occur in the effective reinforcing strength of the fibre having the lower strain to break, and that non-linear, related increases in work of fracture can be obtained. These effects have therefore been exploited to produce compositions having a better balance of stiffness and toughness than do orthodox binary composites.

It is asserted, however, that such synergistic effects may be peculiar to the fibres currently in use. The need to specify accurately the mean strength of fibres from batch to batch has led inadvertently to close control of the strength of individual fibres is to a fairly small scatter of fibre strength about the mean. In simple composites which must have a high interlaminar shear strength for other engineering reasons, fibre failures are then consecutive rather than random, and sensitivity to fine defects and notches is also commonly observed. It is therefore suggested that hybrid mixtures made on a fine scale are a means of suppressing consecutive failure in one fibre type, which in turn allows it to be very strongly bonded and to develop the high reinforcing strength associated with a short stress-transfer length.